

Software use in retracted papers

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Abstract

In this research-in-progress paper, we report preliminary findings of an investigation of the relationship between software and article retraction by analyzing the software mentioned in scholarly articles. We compare the software use of 3,271 retracted publications against 32,710 control papers equally distributed in publication date, scientific domain, and journal rank in an automatic, large-scale analysis. Our findings provide evidence that software use in retracted articles differs from the control group.

Introduction

Retraction is a self-correction mechanism established in the scientific community (Ajiferuke, 2018). The number of article retractions has increased throughout the last decades in absolute and relative numbers (Van Noorden et al., 2011; Steen, 2011; Shuai et al., 2017; Oransky, 2022). Different reasons for this increase have been described (Steen et al., 2013), one of which is lower barriers to publishing flawed articles. For retraction itself, there are also several possible reasons. The two most prominently investigated reasons are misconduct and errors, where misconduct refers to scientific fraud and has been suggested to be performed deliberately (Steen, 2010). Early work indicates that error is the most common reason (Steen, 2011), while later results suggest that misconduct is more likely as its number was previously underestimated (Fang et al., 2012).

While anecdotal evidence for the relation between software and retraction exists and software has previously been associated with errors in investigations, there has been no systematic analysis of the differences in the scientific software landscape of retracted articles. This study investigates the relationship between software and retraction by analyzing the software landscape of retracted articles. For this purpose, we analyzed a set of 3,271 retracted articles in comparison to 32,710 non-retracted control articles. As a result, we identified different usage patterns between the retracted and the control group articles. The next step in this research will compare the citation practice as well as software type (e.g., commercial vs. open source) between the software use in retracted and control group papers.

Materials and methods

We built the current work based on our prior research deliverable named SoftwareKG (Schindler et al., 2022) and the pipeline for automatic identification of software mentions, associated information, relations between them and their disambiguation.

We obtained a list of current retracted papers from Retraction Watch (RW) on January 6th, 2022, and considered all articles published between 2000 and 2019 in our analyses. We

excluded earlier publications because too few data samples are available per year, while later publications are excluded because full-text information is only available up to 2019 from S2ORC. We use RW's information on the original article DOI and publishing journal for identification and utilize the retraction reason for analyses. Full texts for automatic identification of software mentions were obtained from the S2ORC corpus. The S2ORC corpus (Lo et al., 2020) contains numerous English academic papers with meta-data and plain, full-text documents for a subset of papers. We obtained the latest version of the S2ORC corpus (20200705v1), which contains full texts for articles published before April 2020. We used article DOIs and the publishing journal for identification and information on the research domain and publication year to select control articles.

We selected suitable, non-retracted control papers for our analyses by Coarsened Exact Matching (Iacus et al., 2012). The idea is to generate a set of control articles for the given retracted articles, which is equally distributed in all variables that are attributed an influence on the dependent variable. The literature (Schindler et al., 2022) has identified three variables influencing software usage and citation habits: publication date, scientific domain, and journal rank. We control those variables on an article basis as follows: publication date is coarsened to the year of publication; scientific domain is matched exactly, keeping the order of domains intact as we consider the first named domain the most influential for multi-disciplinary work; journal rank based on SCImago (SCImago, n.d.) is coarsened to percentiles determined yearly. Based on the controlled variables, we randomly selected 10 controls from the available S2ORC data for each article without replacement. Overall, 96.9% (3271 out of 3374) of articles were matched, while the remaining unmatched articles were excluded from further analyses. As a result, 3,271 retracted articles published between 2000 and 2019 were analyzed and compared to ten non-overlapping control samples for each article, resulting in an overall control set of 32,710 articles.

Retraction Watch data is available from The Center for Scientific Integrity, the parent nonprofit organization of Retraction Watch, subject to a standard data use agreement (details at <https://retractionwatch.com/retraction-watch-database-user-guide/>). Additionally, we published anonymized aggregated information on software in retracted articles with permission of Retraction Watch to allow direct repeatability of the described statistical analyses. S2ORC data is available for non-commercial use upon requesting access (details at <https://github.com/allenai/s2orc#download-instructions>). The SoftwareKG information extraction pipeline is available from Github (details at <https://github.com/dave-s477/SoMeNLP>), and SoftwareKG data is available from Zenodo (details at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5780121>).

Results

The frequencies for the mentioned software differ in retracted articles, illustrated in Figure 1. SPSS is the most frequently used software in both sets, but there is a high difference in the number of articles mentioning it, with 35.8% of retracted and 20.3% of control articles, respectively. Prism and ImageJ are also central software in both sets, which are mentioned more in retracted articles with 13.3% and 12.7% compared to 9.8%, 8.4% in the control set. A high difference can be observed for R, used in only 4.6% of the retracted articles, while being the third most common software in the control set (9.0%). TargetScan is a noticeable case as it is mentioned in 7.9% of retracted articles but only in 1.0% of control articles. A closer analysis concerning retraction reasons revealed that TargetScan is mostly mentioned within articles retracted due to error, investigation, self-plagiarism, other and especially in paper mill, where

39.7% (95% CI: [33.2, 46.3]) of retracted and 3.7% (95% CI: [2.8, 4.7]) of control articles mention the software.

Figure 1. Proportion of retracted and control articles mentioning software out of the top 20 most used software. Error bars indicate 95% CIs.

A closer look at the most common statistic software showed that the distribution is strongly skewed towards SPSS and Prism in the retracted set. In contrast, a more diverse set of tools is employed in control articles, indicated by higher usage of R, SAS, Excel, Matlab, and Stata. This led us to further investigate the overall distribution of software by analyzing how many articles mention any of the top n software. By analyzing the cumulative distribution of the n most frequently used software, we found that less software is used in a higher number of articles in the retracted set. In detail, for retracted articles, the top 1 software covers more than 25% of articles while the top 2 software are required to cover 25% in the control set. This difference increases to top 3 compared to top 7 software at 50% of articles and top 21 to top 74 at 75%.

Software is often not mentioned by its original name, but authors use spelling variations, abbreviations, or full forms (Schindler et al., 2022). We analyzed how individual software is indicated in retracted articles but did not observe any systematic trend. Retracted articles, for instance, mentioned SPSS less diverse compared to control articles by mostly adhering to the standard name, while an inverse trend exists for ImageJ. Mentions for Quantity One, on the other hand, are similarly distributed.

Discussions and next steps in the project

Software is an integral part of modern science and thus influences certain aspects of the data analysis and results reported in scholarly articles. Retraction, on the other hand, is an essential mechanism for implementing scientific self-correction (Ajiferuke, 2018). Our preliminary results revealed differences in the scientific software landscape and software citation habits in

retracted articles. Retracted articles indicate less software as well as a less diverse set of software, as observed by the increased usage of the most frequently used software.

Next steps of this research include conducting more granular analysis of software use in retracted papers by retract reasons and by software type such as commercial and open access software. The research will also benefit from comparing citation practices of software between retracted papers and control group papers.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) SFB 1270/2: 299150580.)

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